

IMPERATIVES OF MACHINE MOULDING BLOCK RELIABILITY AND RESPONSIVENESS ON CUSTOMER PATRONAGE IN ADO-EKITI

AKINRUWA T. E. (Ph.D)¹, BANKOLE O. A. (Ph.D)² & AKINRUWA T. E. (Ph.D)³

¹ Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria

² Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

³ Department of Business Administration, National Open University, Nigeria

E-mail: te.akinruwa@acu.edu.ng¹

D.O.I: 10.5281/zenodo.18351946

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Received: 2nd December, 2025

Accepted: 29th December 2025

Published: 22nd January 2026

KEYWORDS: Reliability,
Responsiveness, Customer
Patronage

Publisher: Empirical Studies and
Communication - (A Research
Center)
Website: www.cescd.com.ng

ABSTRACT

Consistent patronage in today's competitive market has strong connection with reliability and prompt assistance customer gets. A lot of studies had been done to define, explain and classify machine moulding blocks, yet, few studies isolate the specific effects of reliability and responsiveness within the context of Nigerian market. Thus, the study ascertained the reliability and responsiveness of Machine Moulding Blocks on customer patronage with special reference to Ado-Ekiti Metropolis. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 2,348 customers of the targeted block industry in Ado-Ekiti. The sample size was 331 using Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Primary data used for the study were gathered through the administration of a structured questionnaire to the respondents. The data obtained were analysed using multiple regression. The study found that reliability and responsiveness of the owners of business has significant effect on the dependent variable. The study concluded that both reliability and responsiveness significantly affect customer patronage of Machine Moulding Blocks in Ado-Ekiti.

INTRODUCTION

Customers are seen to be the most crucial aspect of every commercial organisation. Actually, they may be compared to the blood running through the body of any human. This is because one of the company's goals is to gain a large market share, which will enable it to maintain, sustain, and thrive in a competitive business climate while producing its product. As a result, completing all of the aforementioned tasks may increase consumers' future repurchase

intentions, which are the result of numerous organisational efforts. One of the most critical factors influencing client repurchase intentions is providing the finest service quality possible. Furthermore, providing quality, whether in the form of products or services, is considered a crucial aspect in achieving customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, significant improvements in quality lead to consumer happiness, which has a beneficial impact on future customer loyalty (Ahmed, Nawaz, Usman, Shaukat, Ahmed, & Rehman, 2010). Companies must guarantee that the services they provide are of high quality in order to affect consumer satisfaction (Prasidh, 2018). Customers who are satisfied with their purchases are more inclined to return and promote them to others. Furthermore, the client may become an advertiser without being compensated by the company (Becerra & Badrinarayanan, 2013; Kumar & Gupta, 2016). This makes customer satisfaction a critical motivator for survival, competitiveness, and growth, as well as a key factor in developing customer loyalty (Mokhtar, Maiyaki, & Noor, 2011).

Customers are increasingly viewed as the most important, and they must be regarded not just as kings but also as the individuals who provide food to their tables. As a result, organisations who wish to have a large market share, compete favourably, and make a profit must plan and examine their options carefully. This can only be accomplished when customers appreciate the value of the goods they have purchased (Bankole & Ogundipe, 2023). Block manufacturing is one of the industries that is highly important and is gaining ground as a business in recent times due to an increase in the everyday use of the product, such as in building construction. In addition, the block industry helps workforce employability and benefits small and medium-sized enterprises by increasing economic income and improving the standard of living. Overall, opinion indicated that housing plays a significant part in revitalising economic growth in any country, with shelter being one of the important markers of progress (Ileri, 2010). However, no firm can thrive without increasing consumer patronage, contentment, and brand loyalty. Similarly, no company can produce a healthy profit without satisfying the demands of its clients. Service quality contributes to the strengthening of the customer-organisation connection, suggesting a two-way flow of value. This implies that the client obtains actual value from the connection, which transfers into value for the business in the form of increased profitability and long-term sustainability (Ojo, 2010).

Customers who are dissatisfied or receive insufficient attention are less likely to complain about what they perceive to be of lower value. They occasionally depart to pursue another option (Odhiambo, 2015). A consumer is considered to be loyal if they are willing to repurchase a chosen service or product despite the possibility of switching to another product or service. Customers who make repeat purchases of a company's products or services produce more income and are less expensive to serve than other customers. In today's intense rivalry, technical advancements, new social trends, and a dynamic economic environment have all contributed to vast changes in firms such as the block sector inclusive. Customer expectations have a significant influence on the company's activities, necessitating special attention. There is little question that a company that identifies consumer requirements and desires quicker and better than rivals, produces consistent goods, or exceeds customer expectations is more likely to prosper and be effective (Pirayesh & Khaki, 2011). Given the foregoing, customers have more bargaining power, are better at digesting information, and want the most value for their money. Levitt (Darmawan, Mardikaningsih, & Hadi, 2017) argued that consumers are unpredictable, diverse, ever-changing, short-sighted, obstinate, and generally difficult. Based on the statement, it is clear that enterprises, particularly block sector businesses, must recognise the present circumstances and promptly abandon the poor habit of disregarding their customers' interests to be happy with the quality of their services. Successful customers are treated as well as possible to increase their loyalty to the company.

As a result, the customer strategy is tailored to the company's objective to better serve its consumers (Darmawan et al., 2017). As a result, this study looked at the influence of reliability and responsiveness on consumer demand for machine moulding blocks in the Ado-Ekiti Metropolitan Area.

In a competitive world, organisations can only expand if they satisfy and, by extension, thrill their customers. As environmental unpredictability and volatility rise, paying attention to client requirements and ideas becomes increasingly important for the organisation's survival, development, and continuity. A lot of studies had been done to define, explain and classify machine moulding blocks such as Madara, Namango and Arusei (2016), yet, few studies isolate the specific effects of machine moulding block's reliability and responsiveness within the context of the Nigerian consumer market (Lone & Bhat, 2023; Bankole & Ogundipe, 2023; Pasha & Razashah, 2018). The gap is filled by the study. Therefore, the study focused on the imperative effects of machine moulding block's reliability and responsiveness on customer's patronage.

Significance of the Study

It would help block industry managers and owners understand the impact of product and service quality aspects on consumer patronage. It would also serve as a green signal to inform them of what would help them compete favourably and keep their enterprises afloat in a competitive business climate, allowing them to enjoy a decent amount of the market share, which will undoubtedly increase their profit margins. Thus, profit-making would provide the business owners with the possibility to expand their operations. When there is growth, more jobs are created, wages may be raised, and living standards rise. Furthermore, the government benefits since these business owners will be able to pay taxes, allowing the government to earn more cash and appropriately address the requirements of society. Contractors are also included since it improves the quality of their job, reduces waste, and reduces the likelihood of buildings collapsing. Serve as a rebuttal or refutation of the newly discovered direction of product quality, service quality, and client patronage in the literature as it concerns block industry businesses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reliability

It reflects the ability to deliver promised services precisely and consistently (Ojo, 2010). Similarly, services are given as promised to customers, with precise costs. It also takes note of the timely and methodical fulfilment of promises. Reliability is the most significant feature in dealing with customer service issues and executing services on time, such as providing services on time and preserving error-free records of all activities. Furthermore, reliability is crucial for providing correct order fulfilment, such as accurate quotations, accurate records, accurate billing, and keeping service commitments. This is accomplished by keeping promises to do something, providing the right service, consistency of performance and dependability, service being performed correctly the first time, the company keeping its promises in billing accuracy and record keeping, available merchandise, and error-free sales transactions and records. Reliability also includes correct order fulfilment, accurate records, accurate quotes, accurate billing, accurate commission calculation, and keeping service commitments. To this purpose, Yang et al. (2013) argue that dependability is the most crucial feature in service companies.

Thuy (2014) analyses dependability in the context of services that must be supplied on time to clients, and the delivery time must be determined within the company's promise to its

customers. According to Zeithaml and Parasuraman (1990), service dependability is a crucial duty that the firm must do in order to raise customer satisfaction while also improving the efficiency of the company's production process. On the other hand, Heskett, Jones, Loveman, Sasser, and Schlesinger (1994) argue that service reliability can only be improved through proper training, regardless of whether the company establishes a training and education framework that requires employees to participate to understand the importance of service reliability to the company and its customers. According to Zeithaml and Parasuraman in Thuy (2014), if a corporation is unable to supply services on time, it must do improvement initiatives to strengthen service dependability.

Responsiveness

According to Akpan, Akpan, Francis, and Udiong (2024), it characterises the speed and effectiveness with which the consumer is served. This demonstrates that customers perceive the responsiveness of a product or service's quality in terms of staff willingness and prompt fulfilment of requests. Again, it is stated as the firm's aim and willingness to serve clients (Ojo, 2010). This means that personnel are constantly eager to assist consumers and should have time to reply to their demands. Inform staff of the actual time of service delivery (Shafiq, Shafiq, Din & Cheema, 2013). Another quality of service that plays an important part in exceeding customer expectations is responsiveness, which is defined as employees' readiness and eagerness to provide service, which includes service timeliness. It also includes paying attention to clients' safety and difficulties throughout their transactions, providing personalised attention by personnel, and keeping operation hours convenient. These are critical in meeting consumers' expectations that responsiveness will please them and boost their chances of choosing the organisation.

Thuy (2014) defined service responsiveness as the ability of a corporation to meet the needs of its clients at the correct moment or as promptly as feasible. On the other hand, if the firm fails to reply to customers' enquiries promptly, it will result in consumer discontent, as well as a decline in the company's trust and sales income. Responsiveness is the variable that describes the willingness to assist consumers and deliver timely services. It is the desire and eagerness to serve clients while providing quick service. It includes aspects such as the service provider's hours of operation, personnel civility, and the amount of time the consumer must wait to receive assistance. In other terms, it defines the speed and effectiveness with which the consumer is served. Willingness to assist customers is likely to have a significant and favourable impact on their perceived service quality and satisfaction (Onyeonoro, Ohai, Aniemeké, & Okoloagu, 2024).

Customer Patronage

Customers' loyalty to brands, services, stores, or product categories is known as patronage. Consistent patronage or repurchase from a consumer indicates that the client is firmly dedicated to the business or its products. According to Kotler and Keller (2006), brand loyalists do not analyse the brand; rather, they make a confident purchase based on their previous experiences. Customer patronage refers to the instinct, desire, and consideration inside customers that leads to the purchase of products and services from an outlet. The importance of a client and their patronage is so fundamental that businesses cannot thrive without them. Schiffman and Kanuk (2009) and Kotler and Keller (2006) found that firm capacity, products or attributes, economic situation, political forces, social and psychological factors, situational competition, marketing mix program, and other factors all have a significant impact on customer patronage. Customer patronage has been defined as the idea of repeat purchase behaviour, which may be interpreted as some degree of repeated

purchasing of the same brand by the same customer (Zeithaml 2000). Patronage is linked to the competitiveness, profitability, and even existence of a business. It is consequently a major issue in today's commercial environment. Patronage (amount of patronage per time period) is considerably more crucial in the block business as a whole due to the nature of the items available. In other words, the non-storable nature of hotel services makes guaranteeing consistent patronage a top priority (Olugbemi, Solana, Adewunmi, Aderinto, Ogungbayi, & Akerele, 2020). In the instance of the block sector, the company constantly enjoys consumer patronage when it surpasses their expectations, elevating the customers from basic pleasure to ecstasy. Customers could feel, touch, and see the quality of the goods they were exchanging their value for.

Block Moulding Business Overview

The block production industry has been increasingly important in recent years, since the number of structures being constructed has increased dramatically. This business also improves the employability of workers and benefits small and medium-sized businesses by increasing economic income. Housing is an important factor in reviving economic progress in any country, with shelter ranking among major indices of development (Ileri, 2010). There is an obvious shortage of suitable, affordable, and quality housing for low-income people. Although free markets increase production and creativity, they are nonetheless subject to economic rules. The most essential legislation states that market prices reflect market demand. Because half of the population lives below the median income, market-quality housing fetches market pricing. As a result, markets alone can never provide adequate housing for a country's poorest residents (Smith, 2006). Due to limited resources in developing nations, it is critical to seek solutions to cut building costs, especially for low-income workers. Concrete block building has grown in popularity in recent years, serving as a viable alternative to burnt clay bricks and bush-shaped stones. The majority of commercially available devices for producing concrete blocks are poorly mixed and moulded. A locally built block-making machine would help to reduce manufacturing costs by producing cheaper and more easily available construction blocks. Concrete blocks are made mostly of cement, aggregate (sand, gravel), and water, all of which are widely available in Nigeria (Madara, Namango & Arusei, 2016).

The days of manually moulding blocks, which required greater labour power and energy, are over. There is a propensity for supply disappointment owing to the style of production, and when there is a manpower shortage, as opposed to modern times when technology has taken over. There is a high output with little effort. The design allows for successful mixing and efficient block distribution to affluent clients (Winarno, 2019). Concrete is a popular building material since its ingredients are readily available. Because burnt clay bricks are in scarce supply, concrete blocks are widely used in the construction sector. Concrete blocks are a key component of long-lasting masonry buildings. Concrete blocks are placed one at a time and joined with new concrete cement to create the appropriate length and height of the wall. Typically, they are made of high-mass materials with strong compressive strength and moulded into units that can be carried and handled by a single person. For earthquake structures, lighter materials are preferred since they may greatly lower seismic loads. Concrete blocks are created by combining cement and sand. Indeed, this concrete block cannot serve as a full load-bearing material. Furthermore, they are more porous than normal concrete blocks and must be sealed to keep water out (Winarno, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

Expectancy theory and theory of reasoned action formed the bedrock of this study. According to Vroom's (1964) expectation theory, an individual will choose to perform or act in a certain way because they are motivated to pick a precise action above alternative actions based on what they expect the outcome of that chosen performance to be. The conduct was chosen because the consequence was desirable. The idea of reasoned action proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) demonstrates that any conduct displayed by consumers is dependent on antecedent variables. By implication, it demonstrates that whatever levels of consumer patronage any moulding blocks business has are determined by predictive factors and expectations.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Relationship between Reliability, Responsiveness and Patronage
Source: Adapted from Nuridin (2018)

Figure 2.1 depicts the effect of reliability and responsiveness on customer patronage. In view of this, analysing their effect on the reliability and responsiveness of machine moulding blocks, considering the block firm’s responsiveness to customers and how reliable they tend to determine the level of customer patronage.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. This research employed a descriptive survey research design. Primary source was employed to gather information through a structured questionnaire from target respondents. The population of this study is non-deterministic. This is because block industries in Ekiti State do not keep records of their customers. Data for this study was collected using a closed-ended questionnaire. However, a pilot study carried out on different block industries in Ekiti State suggests that the number of customers that patronise each of the selected block industries varies.

Table 1 Population Distribution

S/N	Block Industry	Average No of Customer Per Month
1	Tagbo Block	386
2	OBC Block	268
3	Oluwole Block	276
4	Al-Wajud Block	306
5	Femi Block	292

6	Ayoola Block	304
7	De-Head Engineering	416
8	Sam Ade Block	100
	Total	2,348

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

From table 1, it is evident that only eight (8) registered block industries out of many block industries were selected. They were selected by their visibility and presumed customer patronage as a result of perceived firm size, equipment and location (Author’s Field Survey, 2025). However, the average number of customers was achieved by employing the service of the counter cashier officers of these selected firms, who assisted in keeping tab of customers' patronage rates over a period of one month and the average was obtained for this study. Customers of the selected block industries constituted the target respondents for this study. The block industries were conveniently selected among others in Ado-Ekiti metropolis. However, three hundred and thirty-one (331) respondents were sampled from the selected eight registered block industries using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size table. Two major techniques were used to analyse the data obtained for the study. The techniques are descriptive and inferential statistic. However, descriptive statistic through frequency table was used to analyse the demographic data of the respondents while inferential statistic through multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data generated from the respondents and to determine the influence of reliability and responsiveness on customer patronage. F-statistic was used to test the level significant of the hypotheses.

$$Cpt = \beta_0 + \beta_1Rps + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

Cpt = Customer Patronage
 β_0 = Intercept
 Rps = Responsiveness
 μ = Stochastic or Error Term

$$Cpt = \beta_0 + \beta_1Rbt + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Cpt = Customer Patronage
 β_0 = Intercept
 Rbt = Reliability
 μ = Stochastic or Error Term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presentation of Respondents’ Demographic Data

. Three hundred and thirty-one (331) respondents were sampled, 315 questionnaires were filled and returned which represented 95% response rate which thus implies that the selected block industry customers’ response rate to the information needed for this study is very high and adequate for data analysis. The response of the respondents is analysed in Table 2. Table 2 indicated that the male distribution is 194 (61.6%) while the female showed 121 (38.4%). Therefore, male customers are more than the female customers. In view of this, it is observed that male patronises block industry more compared to female counterparts. Considering the customers' marital status, 107 (34.0%) of the total respondents are single, 195 (61.9%) are married while 13(4.1%) of the total respondents are divorced. The summary of the response gathered here shows that the larger populations of respondents are married and that they patronise block industry most. It was also shown that 55 (17.5%) of the respondents are below 25years of age, 69 (21.8%) are within the range of 26-35years of age, 85 (27.0%)

respondents are between 36-45 years of age while 106 (33.7%) are above 46 years of age. This indicated that the majority of the respondents were within the age of 46 years which implied that customers within this age patronise block industry the most. From the Table 2, it was also revealed that 143 (45.4%) of the total respondents attended University, 98 (31.1%) of the total respondents attended Polytechnic, 46 (14.6%) of the total respondents attended Colleges, while 28 (8.9%) of the survey respondents attended secondary school which implied that customer who attended University patronises university most. Employment status indicated that 95 (30.2%) are employed, 167 (53%) are self-employed while 53 (16.8%) are students. Therefore, most of the customers are self-employed. Patronage mode distribution indicated that 74 (23.5%) patronise block industry weekly, 115 (36.5%) patronise block industry monthly while 126 (40%) patronise block industry yearly. Therefore, most of the respondents patronise block industry yearly.

Table 2: Respondents Demographic Distribution

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	194	61.6
Female	121	38.4
Total	315	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	107	34.0
Married	195	61.9
Divorced	13	4.1
Total	315	100.0
Age		
Below 25	55	17.5
26-35	69	21.8
36-45	85	27.0
46 Above	106	33.7
Total	315	100.0
Academic Background		
University	143	45.4
Polytechnic	98	31.1
College	46	14.6
Secondary	28	8.9
Total	315	100.0
Employment Status		
Employed	95	30.2
Self Employed	167	53.0
Student	53	16.8
Total	315	100.0
Patronage Mode		
Weekly	74	23.5
Monthly	115	36.5
Yearly	126	40.0
Total	315	100.0

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Discussion of Result Based on Specific Hypothesis

Reliability and Customer Patronage of Machine Moulding Blocks

The regression table is an important table to explain the relationship between reliability and customer patronage. The R (Regression Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.681; this indicates that reliability has a strong and positive nexus with customer patronage. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.463, this implies reliability brought about 46.3% variance in customer patronage of machine moulding blocks in Ado-Ekiti. This is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.459, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made the model can only account for 45.9% of reliability in the surveyed block industry. The value of Durbin Watson statistics is 2.000 which showed the absence of autocorrelation in the model due to a large sample. However, reliability and customer patronage which were subjected to multiple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 The F-test is used to test the overall significance of a model by comparing the F calculated with the F tabulated, the comparison is done on Table 3. The table shows that the calculated value of F distribution gives a value greater than the F tabulated. Hence, we accept alternate hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. This implies that reliability will significantly affect customer patronage of machine moulding blocks in Ado-Ekiti.

The multiple regression equation of the model is:

$$\text{Customer Patronage} = 2.023 + 0.400R_{lb}$$

Table 3: Regression Results of Reliability on Customer Patronage

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std Error	T value	P Value
	0.681	0.463	0.459				
Reliability				.400	.026	15.280	.001
Constant				2.023	.294	6.880	.000
Durbin Watson 2.000 F-Cal 117.018 * F-Tab 4.26							

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Responsiveness and Customer Patronage of Machine Moulding Blocks

The regression table is an important table to explain the effect of responsiveness on customer patronage. Table 4 the R (Regression Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.730; this indicates responsiveness has a very strong and positive relationship with the customer patronage. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.532, this implies that responsiveness brought about 53.2% variance in customer patronage of machine moulding blocks in Ado-Ekiti. This is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.527, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made the model can only account for 52.7% of responsiveness in the surveyed block industry. The value of Durbin Watson statistics is 2.699 which showed the absence of autocorrelation in the model due to a large sample. However,

responsiveness and customer patronage were subjected to multiple regression analysis as shown in Table 4. The F-test is used to test the overall significance of a model by comparing the F calculated with the F tabulated, the comparison is done on the table 4. The table shows that the calculated value of F-calculated distribution gives a value lesser than the F-tabulated. Hence, we accept alternate hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. This implies that responsiveness significantly affects customer patronage of machine moulding blocks in Ado-Ekiti.

The multiple regression equations of the model are:

$$\text{Customer Patronage} = 1.713 + 0.534Rps$$

Table 4: Regression Results of Responsiveness on Customer Patronage

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std Error	T value	P Value
	0.730	0.532	0.527				
Responsiveness				.534	.046	11.498	.000
Constant				1.713	.165	10.409	.000
Durbin Watson 2.699 F-Cal 102.512 * F-Tab 4.26							

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Reliability and Customer Patronage

From the Table 3, the unstandardized β co-efficient of reliability gives a positive value of 0.400 with $t= 15.280$ and $(P= 0.000 < 0.05)$. This result showed that reliability has a positive effect on customer patronage therefore, it was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for customer patronage is strongly influenced by reliability. However, the higher the T-value, the better the result and the negativity of the result showed that block industry record transactions have made them more reliable and that also builds positive image in the mind of prospective customers and due to the confidence, they display in attending to customers and that the trust customers have in them which has helped to retain most of the customers patronising moulding blocks. This is in line with the findings of Arslan, Iftikhar and Zaman (2015) who investigated the effect of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction: a comparative analysis of Pakistan Telecom Sector. The findings of study reveal that percentages of customer satisfaction change with the service quality dimensions of reliability and empathy. Overall, it can be established that there is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality dimensions of empathy and reliability. Furthermore, Iddrisua, Nooni, Fianko and Mensah (2015) evaluated the relationship between service quality and customer loyalty in the Cellular industry of Ghana. The findings revealed that service quality variables such as Tangibles, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance and Empathy have a positive influence on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction.

Responsiveness and Customer Patronage

From the Table 4, the unstandardized β co-efficient of responsiveness gives a positive value of 0.534 with $t= 11.498$ and $(P= 0.000 < 0.05)$. This result showed that responsiveness has a highly significant effect on customer patronage therefore, it was found significant. This

means that respondents' reason for customer patronage is strongly and positively influenced by responsiveness. However, the higher the T-value, the better the result and the positivity of the result showed that the extent to which customers are satisfied is highly determined by the response time of the block industry staff to customers and that timely response and delivery to customers' demands affect patronage as revealed in Table 4. This is in line with the findings of Badara et al., (2013) examined the direct effect of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in Nigerian Islamic Bank. The study revealed that responsiveness is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction and assurance is a significant predictor of customer loyalty. Furthermore, Ojo (2010) investigated the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in the telecommunication industry with a focus on Mobile Telecommunication Network (MTN) Nigeria. The study reveals that service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction and that there is a positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. Though Badara et al., (2013) and Ojo (2010) were service providers, the current study showed the strength of responsiveness as a strong predictive variable that is capable of enhancing customer patronage not only in service provider firms, also in the firms that are into physical production.

Conclusion

This study investigated reliability and responsiveness as determinants of customer patronage of Machine Moulding Blocks in Ado-Ekiti Metropolis. It was found that reliability has a strongly significant effect on customer patronage and responsiveness has a very strong significant effect on customer patronage all at 0.05 level of significance. However, responsiveness has the highest significant value on customer patronage, meaning that customer values responsiveness to customer service delivery. From the findings, alternate hypotheses were accepted while null hypotheses were rejected thus concluding that reliability and responsiveness are positively related to customer patronage of machine moulding blocks in Ado-Ekiti. **Recommendations**

Consequent upon the findings, it is recommended that block industry management should prioritise quality product and assure customers of product availability without any concern. Also, they must ensure skilful staff are assigned to attend to customers in providing reliable services and ensure effective keeping of records. They must be able to keep to time while dealing with customers and those services must be rendered confidently and perfectly.

Furthermore, it is recommended that responsiveness should be taken seriously by managers of the block industry in terms of accuracy and timely response to complaints, and services required by customers must be maintained to avoid unnecessary delay. The occurrence of errors or mistakes must be avoided to build a positive image in the minds of prospective customers as any little mistake can cost lives. Moreso, customers should be able to have trust and confidence in the management of the block industry and the credibility to deal with them without being duped. Managers should ensure trust and credibility to improve customer patronage.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, I., Nawaz, M. M., Usman, A., Shaukat, M. Z., Ahmed, N., & Rehman, W. (2010). A mediation of customer satisfaction relationship between service quality and repurchase intentions for the telecom sector in Pakistan: A case study of university students. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(16), 3457-3462.

- Akpan, E. F., Akpan, N. B., Francis, U. I., & Udiong, N.J. (2024). Dimensions of service delivery and customer patronage of Akwa Ibom Transport Company (AKTC) in Uyo Metropolis. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 13 (02), 91-109.
- Arslan, M., Iftikhar, M., & Zaman, R. (2015). Effect of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction: A comparative analysis of Pakistan Telecom Sector. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(6), 43- 62.
- Bankole, O. A., & Ogundipe, C. F. (2024). Product quality and customer satisfaction of detergents among Female Undergraduate Students in Federal University of Technology, Akure. *The Entrepreneur: Journal of Entrepreneurship Development Centre*, 1(1), 50-60.
- Becerra, E. P., & Badrinarayanan, V., (2013). The influence of brand trust and brand identification on brand evangelism. *Journal Of Product and Brand Management*.
- Darmawan, D., Mardikaningsih, R., Hadi, S. (2017). The effect of service quality, customer satisfaction and corporate image on customer loyalty in the banking sector in Indonesia. *Journal of Business and Management*, 19(11), 46-51.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention, and behaviour: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Heskett, J. L., Jones, T. O., Loveman, G. W., Sasser, W. E., & Schlesinger, L. A., (1994). Putting the service profit chain to work. *Harvard Business Review*, 105– 111.
- Iddrisu, A., Nooni, I., Fianko, K. & Mensah, W. (2015). Assessing the impact of service quality on customer loyalty: A case study of the cellular industry of Ghana. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(6), 15- 30.
- Ileri, F. (2010). Monday View, *Daily Nation*, 27
- Kotler, P., & Keller., K. L. (2006). *Marketing management*. Prentice–Hall. United Kingdom
- Krejcie, R, V & Morgan, D. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607-610.
- Kumar, M., & Charles, V. (2010). Evaluation of major factors in the delivery of service quality of retail banks. *Journal of internal reliability and quality management*, 25(2), 210- 245.
- Kumar, V., & Gupta, S., (2016). Conceptualizing the evolution and future of advertising. *Journal of Advertising*, 45(3), 302-317.
- Lone, R. A., & Bhat, M. A. (2023). Impact of product quality on customer satisfaction: Evidence from selected consumer durables. *International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation*, 8(4), 1014-1024.
- Madara, D. S., Namango, S. S., & Arusei, D. (2016). Innovative conceptual design of manual- concrete-block- making-machine. *Innovative Systems Design and Engineering*, 7(7), 41-52.
- Mokhtar, S. S., Maiyaki, A. A., & Noor, N. M. (2011). *The Relationship between Service Quality and Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty in Malaysian Mobile Communication Industry*. School of Doctoral Studies European Union, 32-38.
- Nuridin. S. E. M. M. (2018). Effect of service quality and quality of products to customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as intervening variable in PT. Nano Coating Indonesia. *International Journal of Business and Applied Social Science*, 4(1), 19 -31.
- Odhiambo, M. R. (2015). Effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in Banking Industry: A case study of Kenya Commercial Bank. United States International University Africa Summer.
- Ojo, O. (2010). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in the Telecommunication Industry: Evidence from Nigeria. *Brand Broad Research in Accounting, Negotiation and Distribution*, 1, (1), 88-100.

- Olugbemi, M. T., Solana, O. I., Adewunmi, R. D., Aderinto, A., Ogungbayi, G. B., & Akerele, E. O. (2020). Assessment of factors influencing patronage of Hotels in Ikorodu Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Kampala International University Journal of Humanities*, 5(1), 249-255.
- Onyeonoro, C. O., Ohai, P. N., Aniemeke, C. N & Okoloagu, C. U. (2024). Service quality and customer patronage: A moderating role of staff remuneration, *European Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 12(2), 1-30.
- Pasha, M. A., & Razashah m. (2018). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction: An empirical study in selected Public and Private Sector Banks. *Journal of Arts, Science and Commerce*, 9(1), 64-73.
- Pirayesh, N. M. A., & Khaki, D. M. (2011). Measure the impact of a company's processes and projects on customer satisfaction index. *Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(3), 145-170.
- Prasadh, R.R., (2018). Examining the roles of perceived quality and customer satisfaction as predictors of customer loyalty in the Indian E-Banking Context. *Journal of Management Research*, 18(3), 176-187.
- Schiffman, L. G., & Kanuk, L. L. (2009). *Consumer behaviour: (9th ed.)*. New Jersey: International Edition.
- Shafiq, Y., Shafiq, I., Din, M. S., & Cheema, K. U. R. (2013). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction: A Study of Hotel Industry of Faisalabad, Pakistan. *International Journal of Management and Organizational Studies*, 2(1), 49-54.
- Smith, D.A. (2006) Housing the World's Poor, The four essential roles of government, *Harvard International Review*
- Thomas, J., Page, J., & Spreng, R. A. (2002). Difference scores versus direct effect in service quality measurement. *Journal of Service Resources* 4, 184-192.
- Thuy, L. N. (2014). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction of thien huong corn wine Company in Vietnam. *Department of Business Administration, I-Shou University Master Thesis*
- Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and Motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- Winarno, S. (2019). Comparative strength and cost of rice husk concrete block. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 280.
- Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A. & Berry, L.L. (1990). *Delivering quality service balancing customer perception and expectations*. The Free Press, New York
- Zeithaml, V. A. (2000), Service quality, profitability and the economic worth of customers: what we know and what we need to learn. *Academy of Marketing Science Journal*, 28(1), 67-85.